
239. Actinide-boost stars

THE ELEMENTS found in stars reflect the composition of the interstellar medium from which they formed. But an understanding of their origin, especially in the case of the heavier elements, remains highly incomplete (e.g. Cowan et al., 2021). My short introduction can only touch on the complexities of this subject.

Elements heavier than iron (found in halo stars, the interstellar medium, dust grains, meteorites, and Earth), are mainly formed by the process of neutron-capture.

At low neutron densities, heavy element production occurs via *slow* neutron-capture (termed the *s-process*). The process is ‘slow’ in the sense that there is sufficient time for possible radioactive decay to occur before another neutron is captured. Extending over thousands of years, it occurs in the He-burning layers of asymptotic giant branch stars and during the He- and C-burning phases of massive stars, seeded by iron nuclei from earlier supernovae (Busso et al., 1999; Käppeler et al., 2011).

High neutron densities enable heavy-element nucleosynthesis by *rapid* neutron-capture (the *r-process*). This involves a succession of neutron captures by heavy seed nuclei. The process is rapid in the sense that the nuclei cannot have time to undergo decay before another neutron is captured. It is inferred to occur over timescales of seconds, and is therefore presumably restricted to explosive environments. Possible sites include core-collapse supernovae, and neutron star-neutron star or neutron star–black hole mergers (e.g. Martínez-Pinedo et al., 2014; Côté et al., 2019; Cowan et al., 2021; Vieira et al., 2023; Wanajo et al., 2024).

This NASA [Astronomy Picture of the Day](#) provides a visual synopsis of the likely origin of the elements.

CONSTRAINTS ON these processes can be gained from the overall atomic mass distribution in specific objects. High-resolution optical spectroscopy provides access to some 20–30 elements heavier than the iron-group in late-type (FGK) stars. A dozen others (including Ge, As, Se, Cd, Te, Lu, Os, Ir, Pt, Ag, and Pb) are accessible to near-ultraviolet spectroscopy, for example using HST-STIS (e.g. Sneden et al., 1998; Cowan et al., 2005; Roederer & Lawler, 2012).

WITHIN THIS bigger panorama, the *actinides* are a series of 15 radioactive metallic elements with atomic numbers 89 to 103: actinium (hence their name) to nobelium. *Naturally occurring* (and long-lived) uranium (U) and thorium (Th), and synthetically produced plutonium (Pu), are the most abundant. Like the lanthanides (of which I looked at cerium in essay 91), they form a family with similar if wide-ranging properties.

ACTINIDES PLAY a role in several areas of astrophysics. Nucleo-cosmochronology, which started with the work of Fowler & Hoyle (1960), exploits the very long half-lives of ^{232}Th , ^{235}U and ^{238}U to derive ages within the solar system and beyond (e.g. Cowan et al., 1991; Meyer & Truran, 2000; Goriely & Arnould, 2001).

Determining nuclear-based *stellar* ages developed from the first detections of Th and U in a number of very metal-poor stars, amongst them the ‘neutron-capture-rich’ giant CS 22892–052 (McWilliam et al., 1995; Sneden et al., 1996; 2003), and the r-process rich CS 31082–001 (Cayrel et al., 2001; Hill et al., 2002). Incidentally, Hill et al. (2002) gave abundances for 44 elements, while Sneden et al. (2003) gave abundances or upper limits for 57.

Shorter-lived actinides have also been detected in Galactic cosmic rays, providing potential constraints on their acceleration sites (e.g. Westphal et al., 1998; O’Sullivan et al., 2001; Lingenfelter et al., 2003).

AS DETAILED by Holmbeck et al. (2020), the relative level of (lanthanide) Eu to Fe abundance in a star is a proxy for how much r-process enhancement preceded the star’s formation, compared to the chemical evolution of that gas from supernova events. Stars over-enhanced with Eu relative to Fe compared to the Sun are called ‘r-process enhanced’, and are divided into two categories: r-I, with $0.3 < [\text{Eu}/\text{Fe}] \leq 1.0$ (i.e., a factor 2–10 greater than solar), and r-II, with $[\text{Eu}/\text{Fe}] > 1.0$ (i.e., more than a factor 10 greater than solar).

As underlined by Holmbeck et al. (2020), these stars are relics of prolific r-process event(s) that occurred before the gas was enriched by supernovae, and are therefore considered tracers of nearly pure r-process events.

OF THE VARIATIONS in elemental abundances of stars enhanced with r-process elements, the variation in the actinide-to-lanthanide ratio is one of the most significant. Stars with an over-abundance of [Th/Eu] relative to the solar system are widely referred to as ‘actinide-boost’ stars, occurring in 30% of r-process enhanced stars (e.g. Holmbeck et al., 2020).

By 2014, just six actinide-boost stars were known: CS 31082–001 (as above; with CS designating the Curtis Schmidt survey), CS 30306–132 (Honda et al., 2004), CS 31078–018 (Lai et al., 2008), HE 1219–0312 (Hayek et al., 2009), CS 30315–029 (Siqueira Mello et al., 2014), and HE 2252–4225 (Mashonkina et al., 2014). Other discoveries since include 2MASS J09544277+5246414, identified from LAMOST (Holmbeck et al., 2018), and SPLUS J142445.34–254247.1, identified from the 12-filter S–PLUS Survey (Placco et al., 2023).

A KEY QUESTION is then whether such high actinide abundances result from conditions different to those in other r-process enhanced metal-poor stars. For example, does it depend on how neutron-rich the ejecta from an r-process event may be?

While still considering that ‘*the astrophysical production site of the heaviest elements in the Universe remains a mystery*’, Holmbeck et al. (2019) concluded that all observed levels of actinide enhancements, including those of the ‘actinide-boost stars’, do not necessarily demand distinct r-process progenitors if such a process (such as a neutron star merger) can generate the requisite variations in the neutron flux of its ejecta (Holmbeck et al., 2020).

G AIA ENTERS the discussions, providing distances and proper motions for the first time, with the discovery of three of the latest r-process enhanced stars.

For the $G = 13.8$ mag SPLUS J1424–2542, with an estimated age of 10.1 Gyr, (Placco et al., 2023) identified 36 elements, from C to Th. With $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -3.39$, it has the highest known Th/Eu ratio. The Gaia DR3 parallax, $\varpi = 0.0796 \pm 0.0182$ mas, places it at $1/\varpi = 8.13^{+1.41}_{-1.05}$ kpc, with a (Bayesian) photo-geometric distance 7.82 kpc.

From the Gaia proper motions and line-of-sight velocity, they inferred that it belongs to the Galaxy halo, although not to any of the known halo streams. From a comparison of its abundances with Pop III supernova nucleosynthesis yields, the r- and s-process fractions, and simulations of neutron star mergers, they concluded that its heavy elements resulted from r-process event(s) only, with no contributions from the s-process.

Remarkably, their models imply that its nascent gas cloud was enriched by at least two progenitor populations: a supernova explosion from a metal-free star of mass $11.3 - 13.4 M_{\odot}$, and the aftermath of a binary neutron star merger with masses $1.66 M_{\odot}$ and $1.27 M_{\odot}$.

LAMOST J1124+4535 is r-process-enhanced, although not an actinide-boost star. Xing et al. (2024) derived an age of ~ 11.3 Gyr through radioactive-decay dating, on the assumption that the r-process material was produced by a single event immediately preceding the star’s formation. The abundances suggest that it was accreted from a disrupted dwarf galaxy similar to the surviving Ursa Minor (UMi) dwarf galaxy.

From the Gaia DR3 parallax ($\varpi = 0.09 \pm 0.02$ mas) and proper motion, they infer a distance 7.6 kpc, and a radial orbit with eccentricity $e = 0.53$. The star is associated with an r-II cluster, itself dynamically associated with the LMS–1/Wukong stream (Hattori et al., 2023). This suggests that LAMOST J1124+4535 is the remnant of a disrupted dwarf galaxy with mass similar to that of UMi.

S UBARU–HDS spectroscopy of the $V = 11.5$ mag, very metal-poor ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -2.38$), r-process-enhanced ($[\text{Eu}/\text{Fe}] = 0.80$), actinide-boost LAMOST J0804+5740, gave abundances for 48 species (Lin et al., 2025). They evaluated three r-process models: a neutron star merger (Just et al., 2015), a **collapsar** model (He et al., 2024), and the magnetorotationally-driven **jet supernova** model (Nishimura et al., 2017). They found that the latter successfully reproduced the actinide-boost signatures.

At a Gaia DR3 distance of 3.05 ± 0.18 kpc (Anders et al., 2022), and based on the DR3 proper motion and radial velocity, Zhang et al. (2024) had already shown that LAMOST J0804+5740 is a member of the Gaia Sausage–Enceladus (GSE) stream. This first such GSE actinide-boost star provides new insights into r-process nucleosynthesis in accreted dwarf galaxies.

F ROM 27 million Gaia DR3 stars, Li et al. (2024) used their kinematics (and actions) to identify more than 160 000 *ex situ* stars, with 0.1%, 1.6%, and 63.2% members of the thin disk, thick disk, and halo respectively. From the same sample, Lin et al. (2025) found that 2/3 of the known actinide-boost stars are *ex situ*, and thus more likely to originate from accreted dwarf galaxies.

This scenario in which the r-II stars formed in an extremely neutron-rich environment in which a rare astrophysical event occurred, is supported by the ultra-faint dwarf galaxy, Reticulum II, where most members are highly enhanced in r-process elements (Ji et al., 2016; Roederer et al., 2016). Other r-enhanced dwarf galaxies accreted by the Milky Way will have deposited many r-II stars in the Galactic halo with similar orbital actions.

Hattori et al. (2023) used Gaia DR3 to construct the orbital actions of 161 r-II stars in the solar neighbourhood. They found 6 clusters of r-II stars that have similar orbits and chemistry (one was a new discovery). These clusters are therefore inferred to be good candidates for remnants of completely disrupted r-enhanced dwarf galaxies that merged with the ancient Milky Way.